

Fine-tuning BERT

Version 1.1

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Abstract

This paper describes how to fine-tune the BERT Transformer encoder model for the benchmarks MNLI, SQuAD v1.1., SQuAD v2.0, and SWAG. After carefully introducing the mathematical and BERT-specific notation, it discusses not only the fine-tuning phase but also the evaluation phase and the most common measure applied to the respective benchmark (Accuracy, F_1).

Keywords: Machine Learning; Large Language Models; BERT Transformer Encoder; Benchmarks; Fine-Tuning; Evaluation; Measure

1 The BERT Transformer Model

The BERT Transformer model has proven highly influential in natural language processing, largely due to its effectiveness across a wide range of downstream tasks, achieved through its novel bidirectional pre-training approach (Devlin, Chang, Lee, & Toutanova, 2019).

BERT stands for **B**idirectional **E**ncoder **R**epresentations from **T**ransformers and it represents—as the name suggests—the encoder side of the Transformer architecture. The Transformer architecture was introduced in 2017 by the seminal paper “Attention Is All You Need” (Vaswani et al., 2023).

2 Notation

2.1 Mathematical notation

We define the following notation.

- The field of real numbers is denoted as \mathbb{R} .
- Lower case bold latin letters denote vectors, e.g., $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}$.
- Upper case bold latin letters denote matrices, e.g., $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}$.
- $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{R}^B$ denotes that the vector \mathbf{a} is real-valued and has B rows.
- $|\mathbf{a}|$ denotes the number of elements in the vector \mathbf{a} .
- $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{R \times C}$ denotes that the matrix \mathbf{A} has real-valued entries, R rows, and C columns. R and C are the *dimensions* of the matrix \mathbf{A} .
- $\mathbf{A}_{(r,c)}$ denotes the *element* of matrix \mathbf{A} in row r and column c .
- \mathbf{AB} and $\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B}$ denotes matrix multiplication. Note that the latter notation does *not* denote the Frobenius inner product throughout this document.

We use the term “pseudo-probabilities” to emphasize that the normalized scores of the fine-tuned BERT models are *not* calibrated probabilities but a result of a non-linear normalization process.

2.2 BERT Notation

sentence A *sentence* is an arbitrary span of contiguous text and not necessarily a linguistic sentence.

sequence A *sequence* refers to tokenized input sentence(s) to BERT. Either one sentence \mathbf{A} or two sentences \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} separated by the [SEP] token are possible.

token t A *token* t is an instance of an atomic unit defined in the token vocabulary V of the BERT model. V is generated by the WordPiece tokenizer algorithm (Schuster & Nakajima, 2012; Wu et al., 2016) and augmented by special tokens.

hidden state vector A *hidden state vector* refers to a dense, real-valued representation of a token in a sequence that captures syntactical and semantic contextual information. It is a high-dimensional vector of

size H , produced by the model’s transformer encoder layers. The final hidden state vector for the i^{th} input token is denoted as $\mathbf{h}_i \in \mathbb{R}^H$.

[CLS] The special classification token at the start of the input sequence. Its final hidden state vector is denoted as $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^H$.

[SEP] The special token that marks the end of the first sentence (A). When processing sentence pairs, it also separates sentence A from sentence B and marks the end of B. Its final hidden state vector is denoted as $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{R}^H$.

token embedding \mathbf{e}_t The *token embedding* vector $\mathbf{e}_t \in \mathbb{R}^H$ is the result of applying the learned linear embedding projection to an arbitrary token t . \mathbf{e}_t has *no* segment or positional information added.

segment embedding \mathbf{e}_s The *segment embedding* vector $\mathbf{e}_s \in \mathbb{R}^H$ contains the information whether the corresponding token t belongs to sentence A or B.

position embedding \mathbf{e}_p The *position embedding* vector $\mathbf{e}_p \in \mathbb{R}^H$ represents the *absolute* position of token t in the input sequence.

input embedding \mathbf{e} The *input embedding* vector $\mathbf{e} \in \mathbb{R}^H$ is the sum of $\mathbf{e}_t + \mathbf{e}_s + \mathbf{e}_p$ vectors for an arbitrary token t in the sequence.

3 MNLI Benchmark

According to the BERT paper, the

“Multi-Genre Natural Language Inference [benchmark] is a large-scale, crowdsourced entailment classification task, (Williams, Nangia, & Bowman, 2018). Given a pair of sentences, the goal is to predict whether the second sentence is an entailment, contradiction, or neutral with respect to the first one.”

3.1 Fine-tuning for the MNLI benchmark

MNLI is a classification problem. As stated above, the model has to classify the relationship between two sentences A and B. The model has to choose one out of three classes {entailment, contradiction, neutrality}. Let K denote the number of classes, so $K = 3$ in our case.

3.1.1 General Approach

The fine-tuned model outputs a vector $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^K$ containing K elements (p_1, \dots, p_K) which satisfy $\sum_{i=1}^K p_i = 1$. Every p_i represents a pseudo-probability for the corresponding class $i \in \{1, \dots, K\}$. We choose class

$$i = \operatorname{argmax}_{j \in \{1, \dots, K\}} p_j, \quad (1)$$

i.e., the class with the highest p_j , as the solution to our classification problem.

To compute the pseudo-probabilities for \mathbf{p} we use the softmax function:

$$\mathbf{p} = \operatorname{softmax}(\mathbf{z}) = \operatorname{softmax}([z_1, \dots, z_K]^T) = \left[\frac{e^{z_1}}{\sum_{j=1}^K e^{z_j}}, \dots, \frac{e^{z_K}}{\sum_{j=1}^K e^{z_j}} \right]^T \quad (2)$$

How is the vector \mathbf{z} computed?

We introduce a weight matrix \mathbf{W} that contains additional learnable parameters added to the model during fine-tuning. This is a standard procedure in neural network training.

The pre-trained BERT model outputs final hidden state vectors for all input tokens, including \mathbf{c} (for the [CLS] token) and \mathbf{s} (for [SEP] tokens). The hidden state vector \mathbf{c} was used during *pre-training* for the Next Sentence Prediction (NSP) task, leveraging the rich representations learned by all layers through both “Masked Language Modelling” (MLM) and NSP. Thus, \mathbf{c} incorporates information about the relationship between two input sentences. The precise encoding of this information in \mathbf{c} is not fully understood. However, it is common practice for sequence-level classification tasks like MNLI to rely solely on \mathbf{c} and ignore the hidden vectors of the other tokens in the output sequence.

To compute \mathbf{z} , we use \mathbf{c} as input from the last layer of BERT and combine \mathbf{c} with \mathbf{W} . We apply a linear (precisely: affine) transformation to \mathbf{c} in the form of matrix multiplication between \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{c} , thus $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{W} \cdot \mathbf{c}$.

In the next two subsections, we structure this general approach in two layers: one *linear* layer and one softmax layer.

3.1.2 Linear Layer

We use the vector \mathbf{c} of the last BERT encoder layer as input to the linear layer. We introduce a weight matrix $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times H}$ to provide further learnable

parameters to the neural net. Finally, we introduce a result vector $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^K$ to contain the resulting scores (“logits”) for the three relationship classes:

$$\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{W} \cdot \mathbf{c} \quad (3)$$

3.1.3 softmax Layer

To compute the pseudo-probabilities \mathbf{p} for the individual classes, given the vector \mathbf{z} , we apply the softmax function:

$$\mathbf{p} = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{z}) = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{W} \cdot \mathbf{c}) \quad (4)$$

3.1.4 Dimensions of the Matrices

Considering the dimensions:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} \text{Dimensions:} & (K \times H) & (H \times 1) & (K \times 1) & & & (K \times 1) \\ & | & | & | & & & | \\ \text{Matrices:} & \mathbf{W} & \cdot & \mathbf{c} & = & \mathbf{z} & \rightarrow & \text{softmax}(\mathbf{z}) & = & \mathbf{p} \end{array}$$

3.1.5 Training Loss

To fine-tune for the MNLI benchmark, we add the two layers after the last encoder layer. We retrain the *whole* BERT model with the training data set provided by the MNLI benchmark.

To compute the loss \mathcal{L} for fine-tuning, we use the cross-entropy between the *true* label of the input data record, represented as one-hot vector $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^K$ and the vector \mathbf{p} :

$$\mathcal{L} = -\mathbf{y}^T \log(\mathbf{p}) = -\sum_{i=1}^K y_i \log(p_i) \quad (5)$$

3.1.6 Evaluation

We can check the performance of our fine-tuned model with the test data set of the MNLI benchmark. To evaluate the results, the measure *Accuracy* is used:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{number of correctly classified examples}}{\text{total number of examples}} \quad (6)$$

Note that this kind of evaluation is only justified if the number of examples in the different classes is approximately balanced. This is the case for the MNLI benchmark.

4 SQuAD v1.1 Benchmark

According to the BERT paper, the

*“The **Stanford Question Answering Dataset (SQuAD v1.1)** is a collection of 100k crowdsourced question/answer pairs (Rajpurkar, Zhang, Lopyrev, & Liang, 2016). Given a question and a passage from Wikipedia containing the answer, the task is to predict the answer text span in the passage.”*

Note that it is guaranteed that there is an answer to the question in the provided passage.

4.1 Fine-tuning for SQuAD v1.1 Benchmark

For SQuAD, the input to BERT is typically the concatenation of the question and the passage, separated by [SEP] tokens, and with a [CLS] token at the beginning: ‘[CLS] Question [SEP] Passage [SEP]’. The fine-tuning task is to predict the start and end token indices of the answer within the passage.

Let N denote the number of tokens in the passage. The final hidden states of the BERT model for the passage tokens form a sequence of vectors. Let $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times H}$ be the matrix where each row is the final hidden state vector for a token in the passage. N is the number of rows in \mathbf{C} .

In the SQuAD case, we need two learnable vectors: one vector to score the likelihood of a token being the starting position of the answer and one for the ending position. So let $K = 2$. We will concatenate these two vectors to form columns in the learnable matrix \mathbf{W} below.

Our goal is to determine pseudo-probabilities for every token in the passage whether it is the starting or ending token of the answer. Thus, we need a resulting matrix \mathbf{L} with dimensions $N \times K$. Each row of \mathbf{L} represents the scores (“logits”) of the starting and ending position for the corresponding passage token. To compute pseudo-probabilities, we apply a softmax function column-wise to \mathbf{L} .

To achieve our goal, we again combine two layers: a linear layer and a softmax layer.

4.1.1 Linear Layer

We introduce a learnable weight matrix \mathbf{W} and compute

$$\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{W}. \tag{7}$$

- Input: hidden output matrix of the last BERT layer for the passage tokens: $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times H}$.
- Weights: weight matrix $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times K}$
- Output: logit matrix $\mathbf{L} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times K}$

Linear Layer \mathbf{L} for $K = 2$ For \mathbf{L} we have $R = N$ rows, corresponding to the N passage tokens.

And we have $C = K = 2$ columns: the first column represents the scores of the start position and the second column represents the scores of the end position for the respective token.

Note that every element of $\mathbf{L}_{(r,c)}$ is a scalar ($r \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, $c \in \{1, 2\}$).

The structure of \mathbf{L} is then as follows:

$$\left[\begin{array}{cc} \underbrace{[\mathbf{C}_{1,1}, \dots, \mathbf{C}_{1,H}] \cdot [\mathbf{W}_{1,1}, \dots, \mathbf{W}_{H,1}]^T}_{\mathbf{L}_{(1,1)}} & \underbrace{[\mathbf{C}_{1,1}, \dots, \mathbf{C}_{1,H}] \cdot [\mathbf{W}_{1,2}, \dots, \mathbf{W}_{H,2}]^T}_{\mathbf{L}_{(1,2)}} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \underbrace{[\mathbf{C}_{N,1}, \dots, \mathbf{C}_{N,H}] \cdot [\mathbf{W}_{1,1}, \dots, \mathbf{W}_{H,1}]^T}_{\mathbf{L}_{(N,1)}} & \underbrace{[\mathbf{C}_{N,1}, \dots, \mathbf{C}_{N,H}] \cdot [\mathbf{W}_{1,2}, \dots, \mathbf{W}_{H,2}]^T}_{\mathbf{L}_{(N,2)}} \end{array} \right]$$

Every element $\mathbf{L}_{(r,c)}$ is the dot product between the r^{th} row vector of matrix \mathbf{C} and the c^{th} column vector of matrix \mathbf{W} .

4.1.2 Dimensions of the Matrices

Considering the dimensions:

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{Matrices:} \quad \mathbf{C} \quad \cdot \quad \mathbf{W} \quad = \quad \mathbf{L} \\ \quad \quad \quad | \quad \quad \quad | \quad \quad \quad | \\ \text{Dimensions:} \quad (N \times H) \quad (H \times K) \quad (N \times K) \end{array}$$

4.1.3 softmax layer

We apply the softmax function column-wise to the matrix \mathbf{L} (i.e., independently to the column vector of start scores and the column vector of end scores) to get the pseudo-probabilities:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{L}), \mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times K} \quad (8)$$

Precisely, let $\mathbf{l}_1, \mathbf{l}_2$ be the first and second *column* vectors of \mathbf{L} and $\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2$ be the resulting column vectors after applying softmax. Then, we compute:

$$\mathbf{z}_1 = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{l}_1) = \text{softmax}([\mathbf{l}_{(1,1)}, \dots, \mathbf{l}_{(N,1)}]^T) \quad (9)$$

$$= \left[\frac{e^{\mathbf{l}_{(1,1)}}}{\sum_{j=1}^N e^{\mathbf{l}_{(j,1)}}}, \dots, \frac{e^{\mathbf{l}_{(N,1)}}}{\sum_{j=1}^N e^{\mathbf{l}_{(j,1)}}} \right]^T \quad (10)$$

and

$$\mathbf{z}_2 = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{l}_2) = \text{softmax}([\mathbf{l}_{(1,2)}, \dots, \mathbf{l}_{(N,2)}]^T) \quad (11)$$

$$= \left[\frac{e^{\mathbf{l}_{(1,2)}}}{\sum_{j=1}^N e^{\mathbf{l}_{(j,2)}}}, \dots, \frac{e^{\mathbf{l}_{(N,2)}}}{\sum_{j=1}^N e^{\mathbf{l}_{(j,2)}}} \right]^T \quad (12)$$

$\mathbf{z}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^N$ represents the pseudo-probabilities over the passage tokens for being the start of the answer, and $\mathbf{z}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^N$ represents the pseudo-probabilities for being the end of the answer.

4.1.4 Training Loss

To compute the loss \mathcal{L} for training, we use the sum of the cross-entropy between the true start and end positions, represented as one-hot vectors $\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^N$, and the corresponding pseudo-probabilities vectors $\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^N$:

$$\mathcal{L} = - [\mathbf{y}_1^T \log(\mathbf{z}_1) + \mathbf{y}_2^T \log(\mathbf{z}_2)] \quad (13)$$

We apply the log function element-wise on every element of \mathbf{z}_1 and \mathbf{z}_2 .

4.1.5 Answer Span at Inference Time

As a side note, we describe how to compute the start and end positions at inference time because it differs from the procedure used during fine-tuning.

We calculate a score for every possible answer span (i, j) , where i is the start index and j is the end index, and $1 \leq i \leq j \leq N$. The score for a span (i, j) is the sum of the logit for index i being the start and the logit for index j being the end: $\mathbf{L}_{(i,1)} + \mathbf{L}_{(j,2)}$.

Let S be the set of all possible span scores:

$$S = \{(\mathbf{L}_{(i,1)} + \mathbf{L}_{(j,2)}) \mid 1 \leq i \leq j \leq N\} \quad (14)$$

Then S contains the candidate scores for all possible answer spans. We use the maximum score in S to determine the predicted span (k, l) :

$$(k, l) = \underset{\substack{i,j \\ (1 \leq i \leq j \leq N)}}{\text{argmax}} (\mathbf{L}_{(i,1)} + \mathbf{L}_{(j,2)}) \quad (15)$$

The predicted start index is k and the predicted end index is l .

4.1.6 Evaluation

To evaluate the performance of the fine-tuned model, we can use the test dataset of SQuAD v1.1.

We use the F_1 score that balances the precision and the recall:

Precision (P): It measures how many of the predicted tokens in the answer span are correct. It penalizes false positives (predicting a token that is *not* in the true answer).

Recall (R): It measures how many of the true answer tokens were predicted by the model. It penalizes false negatives (*failing* to predict a token that is in the true answer).

F_1 score: It is the harmonic mean between precision and recall. The subscript 1 means that precision and recall are equally weighted in the computation of the harmonic mean.

More formally, let $\{A_T\}$ be the set of all token indices in the true answer span for a given question. And let $\{A_M\}$ be the set of all token indices that our fine-tuned model has predicted as the answer span. Then the

True Positives (TP) are the token indices that are present in both the true answer span $\{A_T\}$ and the model’s predicted span $\{A_M\}$, i.e., $TP = \{A_T\} \cap \{A_M\}$.

False Positives (FP) are the token indices that are present in the model’s predicted span $\{A_M\}$ but not in the true answer span $\{A_T\}$, i.e., $FP = \{A_M\} \setminus \{A_T\}$.

False Negatives (FN) are the token indices that are present in the true answer span $\{A_T\}$ but not in the model’s predicted span $\{A_M\}$, i.e., $FN = \{A_T\} \setminus \{A_M\}$.

Furthermore let $|TP|$, $|FP|$, and $|FN|$ be the number of indices in TP , FP and FN respectively. Then the F_1 score for a given answer by the model to

a question is computed as follows:

$$\mathbf{P} = \frac{|TP|}{|TP| + |FP|} = \frac{|\{A_T\} \cap \{A_M\}|}{|\{A_T\} \cap \{A_M\}| + |\{A_M\} \setminus \{A_T\}|} = \frac{|\{A_T\} \cap \{A_M\}|}{|\{A_M\}|}, \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbf{R} = \frac{|TP|}{|TP| + |FN|} = \frac{|\{A_T\} \cap \{A_M\}|}{|\{A_T\} \cap \{A_M\}| + |\{A_T\} \setminus \{A_M\}|} = \frac{|\{A_T\} \cap \{A_M\}|}{|\{A_T\}|}, \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_1 = \frac{2 * (P * R)}{(P + R)}. \quad (18)$$

The formulae above are used for one predicted answer span to one true answer span for a given question. However, the SQuAD v1.1 benchmark provides multiple true answer spans for a question (up to five).

To compute the F_1 score for a question with multiple true answers, the model produces a single predicted span $\{A_M\}$. The F_1 score is then calculated between this predicted span $\{A_M\}$ and *each* of the provided true answer spans $\{A_{T,1}\}, \{A_{T,2}\}, \dots$. The maximum of these F_1 scores is taken as the F_1 score for that question.

The overall F_1 score for the dataset is the average of these maximum question F_1 scores over all questions in the test set

5 SQuAD v2.0 Benchmark

The SQuAD v2.0 benchmark (Rajpurkar, Jia, & Liang, 2018) allows for the possibility that *no* answer exists in the provided paragraph. This makes it harder for the model to predict a correct answer.

In total, there are 130k examples in the dataset. Approximately 44k examples do not provide an answer to the question. There is approximately a one-to-one ratio of answerable to unanswerable questions in the development and test data sets. But there are approximately twice as many answerable questions in the train dataset as unanswerable ones. Thus, the ratio between the two types of examples is not evenly distributed between the data sets.

5.1 Fine-Tuning for SQuAD v2.0 Benchmark

SQuAD v2.0 fine-tuning is similar to v1.1 (cf. section 4.1), with the key difference being the model’s ability to predict that no answer exists. To enable this, the hidden state of the [CLS] token (**c**) is included as a potential

candidate for both the start and end positions of the answer span, alongside the passage token hidden states.

Let N_P be the number of tokens in the passage. The input sequence to BERT is ‘[CLS] Question [SEP] Passage [SEP]’. The final hidden states for the relevant tokens form a sequence of $N = N_P + 1$ vectors (corresponding to the [CLS] token and the N_P passage tokens). In SQuAD v2.0, N includes the [CLS] token, while in v1.1, it does not. Let $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times H}$ be the matrix where the first row is \mathbf{c} and the subsequent N_P rows are the final hidden state vectors for the passage tokens.

We use the same linear layer as in SQuAD v1.1 (cf. section 4.1.1), applying a weight matrix $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times K}$ ($K = 2$) to the matrix \mathbf{C} to produce a logit matrix $\mathbf{L} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times K}$. The first row of \mathbf{L} contains the start and end scores for the [CLS] token, and the subsequent N_P rows contain the scores for the passage tokens. A column-wise softmax is applied to \mathbf{L} (cf. section 4.1.3) to get pseudo-probabilities over the N possible start positions and N possible end positions.

The training loss is the sum of the cross-entropy losses for the start and end positions, similar to SQuAD v1.1 (cf. 4.1.4). For unanswerable questions, the true start and end positions can be considered as corresponding to the [CLS] token (index 1).

At inference time, it is possible to apply the same procedure as given for SQuAD v1.1 in section 4.1.5 (predicting the highest scoring span among passage tokens). However, there is a second possibility which leads to slightly better results for the F_1 metric according to the authors of the BERT and the SQuAD v2.0 papers.

Threshold τ We introduce a threshold $\tau \in \mathbb{R}$. We are adding this threshold to the null span score (the score of the [CLS] token being the start and end) and comparing the result against the scores of all valid non-null spans. Formally, the predicted span (m, n) is determined as follows (cf. eq. (15)):

$$(m, n) = \begin{cases} (1, 1), & \text{if } (\mathbf{L}_{(1,1)} + \mathbf{L}_{(1,2)}) + \tau \geq \max_{1 < i \leq j \leq N} (\mathbf{L}_{(i,1)} + \mathbf{L}_{(j,2)}) \\ \operatorname{argmax}_{\substack{i,j \\ (1 < i \leq j \leq N)}} (\mathbf{L}_{(i,1)} + \mathbf{L}_{(j,2)}), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

Note that the non-null case prediction is an argmax over spans (i, j) where $i, j > 1$, which excludes the [CLS] token at index 1. Index 1 corresponds to the [CLS] token in the input sequence.

The value of the threshold τ is determined such that it maximizes the F_1 score on the validation data set. So, it is essentially a hyperparameter of the fine-tuned model.

5.1.1 Evaluation

We have to extend the F_1 score to the case that a question does *not* have an answer within the given passage.

For evaluation, an unanswerable question corresponds to an empty set of indices for the *true* answer span, i.e., $\{A_T\} = \emptyset$. This means that $|\{A_T\}| = 0$.

If the model predicts "no answer", this also corresponds to an empty set of indices for the *predicted* answer span, $\{A_M\} = \emptyset$.

The F1 score calculation then proceeds based on these sets:

Case 1: The model predicts that there is *no* answer. This means that $\{A_M\} = \emptyset$, so $|\{A_M\}| = 0$. Since the true answer is also unanswerable, $\{A_T\} = \emptyset$, and $|\{A_T\}| = 0$. Then $TP = (\{A_M\} \cap \{A_T\}) = \emptyset$, and $|TP| = 0$. Thus,

$$\left[\left(\mathbf{P} = \frac{|TP|}{|\{A_M\}|} = \frac{0}{0} \right) \text{ and } \left(\mathbf{R} = \frac{|TP|}{|\{A_T\}|} = \frac{0}{0} \right) \right] \Rightarrow (\mathbf{F}_1 := 1). \quad (20)$$

In the standard SQuAD evaluation, if both the true and predicted sets are empty, F1 is defined as 1.

Case 2: The model predicts that there *is* an answer. This means that the model predicts a span (i, j) , where $1 \leq i \leq j \leq N$ (and not $(1, 1)$), so $\{A_M\} = \{i, \dots, j\}$, and $|\{A_M\}| > 0$. The true answer is unanswerable, so $\{A_T\} = \emptyset$, and $|\{A_T\}| = 0$. Then $TP = (\{A_M\} \cap \{A_T\}) = \{i, \dots, j\} \cap \emptyset = \emptyset$, and $|TP| = 0$. Thus,

$$\left[\left(\mathbf{P} = \frac{|TP|}{|\{A_M\}|} = \frac{0}{|\{A_M\}|} \right) \text{ and } \left(\mathbf{R} = \frac{|TP|}{|\{A_T\}|} = \frac{0}{0} \right) \right] \Rightarrow (\mathbf{F}_1 := 0). \quad (21)$$

Since $|\{A_M\}| > 0$, $P = 0$. In the standard SQuAD evaluation, if $TP = 0$ and $\{A_T\} = \emptyset$, R is taken as 0, leading to $F_1 := 0$.

6 SWAG Benchmark

According to the BERT paper, the **S**ituations **W**ith **A**dversarial **G**enerations (SWAG) dataset

“(. . .) contains 113k sentence-pair completion examples that evaluate grounded commonsense inference (Zellers, Bisk, Schwartz, & Choi, 2018). Given a sentence, the task is to choose the most plausible continuation among four choices.”

6.1 Fine-Tuning for SWAG Benchmark

We construct four input sequences for every sentence-pair example. Each input sequence is a concatenation of a given sentence (A) and a possible continuation (B), typically formatted as ‘[CLS] Sentence A [SEP] Continuation B [SEP]’.

The fine-tuning is analogous to the fine-tuning of the MNLI benchmark (see section 3.1), as both are classification tasks over sentence pairs.

We only use the final hidden state vector of the [CLS] token, \mathbf{c} , and introduce a learnable matrix $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times H}$ with $K = 4$ (see eq. (3), where \mathbf{z} is computed from \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{c}). A softmax function is applied to the resulting vector $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^K$ which gives us the pseudo-probabilities over the four possible continuations of sentence A, i.e., vector $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^K$ (see eq. (4)).

To fine-tune, we minimize the cross-entropy between the learned and the real distribution, or stated equivalently, we maximize the log-likelihood of the learned distribution given the dataset (cf. eq. (5)). To do this, we have to find the optimal parameters of the learned distribution, i.e., the weights of the fine-tuned model.

6.1.1 Evaluation

We use the Accuracy score as given by eq. (6).

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